

Paper 33

A STUDY ON E-BANKING SERVICES IN MANGALURU CITY- CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND AWARENESS

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Abstract

E banking is a method of banking in which the customer conducts transactions electronically via the Internet. Internet banking is changing the banking industry, having the major effects on banking relationships. Electronic banking has many names like e banking, virtual banking, online banking, or internet banking. It is simply the use of electronic and telecommunications network for delivering various banking products and services. Through e-banking, a customer can access his account and conduct many transactions using his computer or mobile phone. It is more helpful because there is lesser transaction costs, a reduced margin for human error, lesser paperwork, reduced fixed costs, more loyal customers. The popular services under e-banking in India are, ATMs (*Automated Teller Machines*), Telephone Banking, Electronic Clearing Cards, Smart Cards, EFT (*Electronic Funds Transfer*) System, ECS (*Electronic Clearing Services*), Mobile Banking, Internet Banking, Telebanking, Door-step Banking. Tap, click and swipe-these are the new sounds of money. Modern technology is fast replacing paper with computer files, and banks too have come a long way from the old days of manually recording transactions in registers and tallying them up at the end of the day.

Keywords: e-banking, internet, advantages, service.

1.INTRODUCTION:

Since technology has penetrated virtually in all spheres of life, banking is no exception to that. The world is changing at a staggering rate and technology is considered to be the key driver for these changes around us .The adoption of technology by the banks brought more reliability , efficiency, security and privacy in it's services ever than before. Today any user with a personal computer and a browser can get connected to his bank's website to perform any of the virtual banking functions. Thus, services of the bank have become more users friendly.

E-banking provides enormous benefits to consumers in terms of ease and cost of transaction, either through internet ,telephone or other electronic delivery, besides it has become one of the most essential technological changes in the financial industry. Many activities are handled electronically due to the acceptance of information technology at home as well as at workplace .thus it made time and distance irrelevant to many transactions.

2.OBJECTIVES:

1. To know the perceptual mapping of internet banking users.
2. To find out the reasons why the customers are using internet banking services.
3. To analyse the general awareness of e-banking among the people.
4. To identify the important factor that influences the customer satisfaction towards E banking.

3.METHODOLOGY:

The research study was conducted to know the peoples’ perception towards e-banking services. This was done through the collection of data from 42 respondents from Mangalore city. The research instruments used in collecting primary data was a questionnaire. The questionnaire and survey was undertaken through the means of google forms. The questionnaire was prepared on the basis of secondary information gathered.

4.DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table -1 Age-wise classification of respondents

Percentage	No. of respondents	Age
7	3	Below 20
83	35	20 to 30
4.76	2	30 to 40
2.38	1	40 to 50
2.38	1	Above 50
100	42	TOTAL

From above diagram, it is noticed that respondents comprising of 83% belong to the age group of 20-30 years, followed by 7% customers belong to the age group of below 20 years.

Table -2 Gender -wise classification of respondents

Percentage	No. of respondents	Gender
64.3	27	Female
35.7	15	Male
100	42	Total

The above table -2 shows that 64.3% are female respondents and only 35.7% are male respondents .

TABLE- 3: Awareness of e-banking services among the people.

percentage	No. of respondents	Scale
90.5	38	Yes
2.4	1	No
7.1	3	May be
100	42	TOTAL

It is revealed from the table -3 that about 90.5% of people aware of e-banking services, provided by the banks.

TABLE -4 About the no. of users of e-banking services.

Percentage	No. of respondents	Scale
83.3	35	Yes
16.7	7	No
100	42	Total

The above diagram, shows that majority ie.83.3% people have been using e-banking services, only 16.7% of people are not using e-banking services.

TABLE: 5 The main reasons for using e-banking services

percentage	No. of respondents	Reasons
10.8	5	Better information
51.4	21	24 hours services
32.4	14	Simplification of process
5.4	2	saves time
-	-	other
100	42	TOTAL

With regard to the main reasons for using e-banking services above diagram -5 shows that 51.4% of the people use the facility because of the 24*7 services of the e-banking. On the other hand 32.4% of the respondents said that it is simplification in the process made them to use e-banking.

TABLE-6 The opinions with regard to the Reasons for, few people not using the online banking service

Percentage	No. of respondents	Reasons
13	5	Do not have internet at home
26.1	11	Find the process too difficult
43.5	18	Don't trust internet services for managing money
17.4	8	Not interested
-	-	other
100	42	TOTAL

From the above table -6 it is evident from the opinions of the 43% of respondents about the reasons some people not using e-banking that it is because they don't trust internet services for managing money ,followed by 26.1%of respondents saying it is because since they find the process too difficult.

TABLE-7 About the trusted level of the security of online banking services

Percentage	No. of respondents	scale
16.7	7	completely
61.9	26	somewhat
14.3	6	unsure
7.1	3	Not at all
100	42	TOTAL

When the respondents are asked to give their views on internet banking services on a scale with regard to the security and privacy, it is found from the table -7 that about 61.9% of the respondents somewhat trust the security level of the internet and 14.3% of respondents opined complete trust with regard to the security and privacy of the internet. Only 16.7% of them are still unsure about it, while 7.1 % of the respondents expressed disappointment with regard to it.

TABLE-8 Opinions about the convenience of manual banking with comparison to the internet banking.

Percentage	No. of respondents	scale
14.3	6	strongly agree
50	21	Agree
31	13	disagree
4.7	2	strongly disagree
100	42	TOTAL

As per the table -8 about the convenience of manual banking with comparison to internet banking, 14.3% of the people considers manual banking is more convenient than that of internet banking by strongly agreeing with it ,followed by the 50% of the respondents agreed with the same . On the other hand 31% of the people disagree saying internet banking is more convenient than that of manual banking services.

TABLE-9 About the most used e-banking service

Percentage	No. of respondents	Types
9.5	4	Checking account
21.4	9	cash management
66.7	28	Debit and credit cards
2.4	1	Business loans
-	-	other
100	42	TOTAL

It is revealed from the table-9 that the usage of e-banking services like debit cards and credit cards services are mostly being used by the people as 66.7% of the responded the same. Rest of the 21.4% of the people said about cash management purpose followed by 9.5% of the response pertaining to the checking account.

TABLE-10 Main disadvantage of e-banking that discourages one from using it

Percentage	No. of respondents	Disadvantages
45.2	19	Security concern
16.7	7	lack of assistance
5.1	2	impersonality services
33	14	Dependent on internet services
-	-	other
100	42	TOTAL

when the respondents are asked about the disadvantages of e-banking services majority ie.45.2% worried about the security issue .rest of the 33.3% of respondents supported the same expressing displeasure about the service dependency on internet .However, it is 16.7% considered disadvantages like lack of assistance and 5.1% of people considered impersonal services as a discouraging factors.

TABLE 11–Opinions with regard to the important factor that influences the customer satisfaction towards internet banking.

Percentage	No. of respondents	Important factors
21.4	9	service quality
-	-	web design &content
35.7	15	security and privacy
42.9	18	convenience and speed
-	-	Other
100	42	TOTAL

From the above table-11 pertaining to the questions regarding to the factors influencing the customer satisfaction towards e banking majority ie.42,9% of the respondents stressed the importance of convenience and speed in the services. and rest of the 35.7% of people said it is security and privacy gives them satisfaction with regard to the services provided .however only 21 .4% of the respondents went with the option of service quality.

TABLE-12 Rating with regard to the overall quality of the e banking services.

Percentage	No. of respondents	Ratings
14.3	6	excellent
42.9	18	very good
40.5	17	good
2.3	1	poor
100	42	TOTAL

with regard to the rating of quality of the e banking services table -12 shows 42.9% of the respondents considers 'very good' and 40.5% of the people consider 'good'. and 14.3% of the people consider e –banking services as excellent.

5. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

- The study is restricted only to Mangalore city.
- Since the survey was conducted through google form, could reach only technically literate people.
- The sample size is limited to 42 only.

6. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- With the help of our study it is found that out of 42 respondents ,majority 90.5% of people are aware of e-banking services provided by the banks.
- Our study also reveals that majority 83.3% of the people have been using e-banking services.
- Besides ,we found out the reasons like 24*7 e-banking services ,simplified process involved in the services are some of the reasons for the frequent use of e-banking services as it made the transaction convenient and easier.
- It is understood with the help of our study that most of the people are worried about the security and privacy issues of the internet as the e-banking services works through internet.
- It is revealed that internet e-banking is more convenient than traditional manual banking services as people opined the same
- It is found that the e-banking services like uses of debit card and credit card are being used by the majority of the people and playing predominant role in the e-banking industry

7. SUGGESTIONS:

- banks needs to focus more on offering standard online services to its customers by providing exceptional customer services through technologies like finger print readers ,card readers, and other new and emerging financial technologies which ensures privacy and reduce fraud concerns.
- Employ ever-evolving biometrics, such as retina scanning, to reduce customer frustrations while increasing online banking security.
- Proper training needs to be given to the bank employees pertaining to the technologies that are being used so that customers will not get any kind of confusion with regard to the uses of new e-banking service.
- The banks should conduct an effective research for making more and more awareness about E banking service.
- The banks have to do new process and strategies to create more security coverage.

8. CONCLUSION:

The paper makes an attempt to understand E banking services. The result of the study shows that convenience and speed is the most important factor that influences the customer satisfaction towards internet banking. Convenience and speed is the top reasons why peoples like online banking. People are more convenient in internet banking than manual banking. So banks have to rethink their strategies to ensure they stay relevant to modern consumers.

To create the awareness of E banking it is very important that, the Government and all the associated bodies should all offer their support in spreading E banking awareness. And it will help to increase the awareness of E banking among the people. Bank should make efforts to increase customer's awareness about internet banking facilities by conducting training programmes.

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Questionnaire on: “A study on E-Banking Services in Mangaluru city- Customer satisfaction and Awareness”

This Questionnaire aims to know the point of view of general public on “E banking services” and to collect their suggestions to alleviate it.

1. Name
2. Age
3. Gender
4. Are you aware of the E banking services provided by banks?
 - Yes
 - No
 - May be
5. Do you use E banking?
 - Yes
 - No
6. If yes, which one is the main reason for you to use E banking?
 - Better information
 - 24 hour service
 - Simplification of process
 - Limited time available
 - Other
7. Do you trust the security of online banking services?
 - Completely
 - Somewhat
 - Unsure
 - Not at all
8. Internet banking is more convenient than manual banking
 - Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
9. Which type of e banking service mostly you use?
 - Checking account
 - Cash management
 - Debit and credit cards
 - Business loans
 - Other
10. Which is the main disadvantage of e banking that discourages you from using?
 - Security concern

- Lack of assistance
- Impersonality service
- Dependent on internet
- Other

11. In your opinion, which is one of the important factors, that influence the customer satisfaction towards internet banking?

- Service factory
- We design and content
- Security and recovery
- Convenience and speed
- Other

12. What do you feel about overall E banking service quality of your bank?

- Excellent
- Very good
- Good
- Poor

13. Suggestions (if any)